

chlorophyll (a+b) concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$ fresh weight) of the plumule after extraction in 80% (wt/vol) acetone. Varieties with the highest concentration of total chlorophyll after this treatment were considered the most cold tolerant.

The greening of etiolated rice seedlings at low temperature varied (see table). In general, chlorophyll synthesis was poor in both indigenous

and exotic rices except for Sinjali, which synthesized 2.5 times more total chlorophyll than Silange and Chhomrong and 15.1 times more than IR36 at 17°C.

Cold-tolerant Seto Bhakunde, Kaloptale, and Darmali showed poor greening at low temperature because they are adapted to warmer environments at germination and early seedling stages.

Correlation between plumule color (1-9 scale) and total chlorophyll (a+b) concentration was significantly negative ($r = -0.772$). This suggests that screening rice varieties for rate of chlorophyll synthesis can be done simply—although crudely—by visually assessing leaf color after cold treatment at 17°C. This method seems to be more appropriate for screening spring season rice whose growth is limited by low temperature at the early growth stage. □

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Study of proteins synthesized in rice roots under salt stress conditions

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Salt levels are gradually increasing in many irrigated rice areas. We studied salt-tolerant IRRI line IR10198-66-2 to find out more about salt tolerance on a molecular basis.

Surface-sterilized seeds were grown on Murashige and Skoog medium (MS) at $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under 14:10 light-dark cycle. We exposed 10-d-old plants to 2% sodium chloride in MS for 48 h. Roots were excised from salt-stressed and nonstressed plants. Proteins were extracted and analyzed by isoelectric focusing in a pH gradient (4-8) in the first dimension and in sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel (12%) electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) in the second dimension. Gels were then silver-stained to visualize the proteins.

Results revealed significant induction of at least two proteins, both with isoelectric points (PI) of about 7 and having 27,000 and 25,500 kD molecular weight in the salt-stressed plants (see figure, a). No such proteins were observed in control gels at the same location (see figure, b).

This study suggests that salt tolerance in rice is not merely a physiological adjustment, but rather that root cells synthesize special proteins under this stress. In nature, such proteins play a specific role under the circumstances in

a) Protein pattern of rice roots obtained with silver-stained two-dimensional SDS-PAGE from 48 hours, 2% NaCl-treated plants (heavily induced proteins are enclosed in the box). Molecular weights (kD) and position of markers are on the left. b) Control.

which they are induced. Elucidating the functions of these proteins can lead to understanding the mechanism underlying salt tolerance. These proteins may also offer a convenient tool for molecular screening of germplasm. □

Variability in salt tolerance of accessions of wild rice species *Oryza punctata* and *O. officinalis*

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We have started a comprehensive salt tolerance screening program for all available wild rice germplasm. In the first phase, six accessions of *O. punctata*—three diploid ($2n=2x=24$ BB) and three tetraploid ($2n=4x=48$ BBCC)—and three diploid accessions of *O. officinalis* ($2n=2x=24$ CC) were tested in the glasshouse. We used the gravel culture technique and natural conditions of temperature (25/15 °C day/night temperature), 10 h light, and 60% relative humidity.

We raised seedlings by planting internode cuttings of stems in plastic pots filled with gravel and Hoagland nutrient solution. The pots were placed in another plastic pot containing nutrient solution to ensure a continuous nutrient supply to the plant and easy replacement of the solution. We planted three cuttings per pot and three pots/accession per species.

When leaves started to appear, we induced artificial salinity with a mixture

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Details of salt tolerance screening of different accessions of 2 wild rice species at 5 periods of growth (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 wk).

Species	Accession no.	Chromosome number and genome	Survival (% of control)				
			2	4	6	8	10
<i>O. punctata</i>	103897 ^a	$2n = 2x = 24$	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103917	BB	66	66	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103903 ^b		33	0	-	-	-
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	$2n=4x=48$	100	100	66	66	66
<i>O. punctata</i>	101389	BBCC	100	100	100	66	33
<i>O. punctata</i>	101408		100	100	66	33	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	103286	$2n=2x=24$	100	100	66	66	33
<i>O. officinalis</i>	104973 ^a	CC	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105322 ^b		33	33	33	0	0
Basmati 370	Susceptible check		0	0	0	0	0
Jhona 349	Tolerant check		100	33	-	-	-

^aMost of the plants died at EC 5-8 dS/m. ^bMost of the plants died at EC 10-11 dS/m.

of Na₂SO₄ CaCl₂, MgCl₂, and NaCl at a ratio of 10:5:1:4 through a stepwise increase in electrical conductivity of 2 dS/m every other day until EC reached 12 dS/m. The entire saline solution was replaced with fresh solution semiweekly.

Susceptible check Basmati 370 died at the onset of EC 8 dS/m; tolerant check Jhona 349 died after 4 wk of growth at EC 12 dS/m (see table). Of the three accessions of *O. officinalis*, 104973 died between EC 5-EC 8 dS/m, 105322 survived for 6 wk, and 103286 survived for 10 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Of the diploid accessions of *O. punctata*, only 103917 survived for 4 wk, while all three tetraploid accessions survived beyond 8 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Accession 105158 survived for more than 12 wk in EC 12 dS/m. The plant was still in the vegetative phase and had only one tiller, but was healthy and green. We are not certain whether the vegetative growth was stressed by the weather during May-Aug, which is hot and dry under local conditions and a dormant period for wild rice species, or by salinity.

The study did indicate, however, that if many wild rice accessions are screened for salt tolerance, tremendous variability can be anticipated, and this can be used for salt tolerance improvement of cultivated rice varieties. As far as we are aware, this is the first report of salt tolerance in wild rice species other than *Porteresia coarctata*. Further studies are in progress. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

PR110, a new bacterial blight (BB)-resistant rice variety for Punjab, India

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PR 106 is a predominant rice variety in the Punjab because of its high yield potential,

long slender grains, and duration that fits very well into a rice - wheat crop rotation. PR106 is, however, susceptible to BB, which is the most serious rice disease in the Punjab.

The State Variety Approval Committee has approved a new BB-resistant rice variety, PR110, for cultivation in the Punjab. PR110 was developed using the backcross

approach, with PR106 as recurrent parent. It inherited BB resistance from Patong 32, a tall photoperiod-sensitive variety from Malaysia. A dwarf homozygous BB-resistant F₃ line of TN1/Patong 32 was used as the female parent in the first cross with PR106, and followed by five recurrent backcrosses with PR106. PR110, from TN1/Patong 32//PR 106*⁶, was